

Biomedical Semantics in the Big Data Era

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Abstract

The availability of large biomedical datasets brings both new challenges and opportunities. At the same time, the resources of biomedical semantics both support the exploitation of these datasets and benefit from them for their own refinement. So the question is neither “What can semantics do for Big Data?”, nor “What can Big Data do for semantics?”. It is “How can Big Data and biomedical semantics best benefit from each other?”.

Both the need of processing natural language or structured documents and of building and maintaining semantic resources like lexicons, thesauri, classifications, and ontologies have fueled a broad range of research and development activities in the field of biomedical and health informatics. In this workshop, we explore both extraction and normalization of knowledge from documents and ontology development.

This workshop, organized by the IMIA WG LaMB (Language and Meaning in Biomedicine) sees in the advance of Big Data technologies a chance for leveraging large amounts of unstructured domain content to build, maintain, and validate semantic resources as well as to tackle decision-support challenges in health and life sciences.

The workshop will exploit the possibilities of the (semi-) automated acquisition of terminology concepts, ontology axioms, as well as term translations and synonyms. It will also discuss the possibilities of improving spelling correction, short form expansion and disambiguation exploiting large corpora using unsupervised or semi-supervised methods. Further, the future of semantic-enabled biomedical decision support systems powered with question-answering and curation of biomedical contents will be discussed.

Keywords:

Natural-language and speech processing; Ontologies, knowledge bases, data models and metadata; Knowledge acquisition and processing.

Workshop Description

Now that Electronic Health Records (EHRs) become increasingly commonplace, the usefulness of the data for clinical and research purposes becomes a pressing issue. However, most of the content of EHRs is constituted by free text, exhibiting special sublanguage characteristics, such as telegram style, short forms, spelling errors, neologisms etc. Medical terminology is highly diverse, with an accentuated

gap between expert and lay expressions in many languages. Given the lack of an emerging structural and encoding (worldwide) practice for clinical data despite the numerous and promising efforts - the application of natural language processing (NLP) techniques is and will be needed. However, NLP approaches do not solely support processing of textual data, they also bear the promise of supporting the construction and maintenance of semantic resources like lexicons, thesauri, classifications, and ontologies.

Together with (clinical) information models these semantic resources play a crucial role in the gradual shift from free-text clinical documentation to structured and encoded clinical documentation. This shows how NLP on the one hand, and semantic resources like terminologies and ontologies on the other hand are complementary rather than competing technologies. Both need to be strengthened, and collaboration and cross-fertilization is needed.

This workshop aims at providing a stimulus for such collaboration in a truly international fashion, providing perspectives from representatives of various working groups of the Associations and Federations of Biomedical and Health Informatics, with a focus on semantic standards and multilingualism.

Workshop Speakers

The speakers in this workshop organized by the IMIA LaMB working group are:

Tomasz Adamusiak, MD, PhD (Thomson Reuters, Boston, MA, USA)

Ronald Cornet, PhD (Academic Medical Center University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands & Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden)

Dr. Jianying Hu, PhD (IBM T. J. Watson Research Center, Yorktown Heights, NY, USA)

Dr. Stephane Meystre, MD, PhD (University of Utah, Salt Lake City, Utah, USA)

Patrick Ruch, PhD (University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland, Geneva, Switzerland)

Stefan Schulz, MD (Medical University of Graz, Graz, Austria)

General Organization of the Workshop Proposal

General Topics

The workshop aims to bring together those stakeholders who are using, developing and maintaining terminological and ontological resources, and those using them to perform biomedical data analytics or decision support. The speakers will address the following topics.

Stephane Meystre is chair of the AMIA NLP working group and a faculty member of the Department of Biomedical Informatics at the University of Utah (Salt Lake City, Utah, USA) with research activities focused on easing access to clinical data for research and clinical care purposes, using techniques such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) for information extraction and automated de-identification, and automating ontologies development and management.

He will present an overview of efforts applying NLP to help build terminological resources from clinical free-text (i.e., electronic health record documents) and details of a semi-automated ontology development and management system (SEAM) developed to create ontologies to support medically unexplained syndromes detection and management among veterans within the U.S. Veterans Health Administration. This SEAM system helps the ontology development by automatically extracting terms, concepts, and relations from narrative text, and then offering a streamlined graphical user interface to edit and create content in the ontology that can finally be exported in OWL format [1][2][3].

Tomasz Adamusiak is chair of the AMIA Knowledge Representation and Semantics (KR+S) working group and a Senior Data Scientist at Thomson Reuters working with Big Data and Linked Data technologies to drive new scientific and strategic insights in target finding, drug repurposing, and precision medicine. He is trained in clinical informatics at the U.S. National Library of Medicine, and bioinformatics at the European Bioinformatics Institute in Cambridge, UK. Dr. Adamusiak has extensive experience in secondary use of EHR data, clinical terminologies, and predictive analytics.

He will present his experiences with applying semantic technologies for knowledge discovery in health care[4][5][6].

Stefan Schulz is Chair of the IMIA working group “Language and Meaning in Biomedicine” (LaMB) and a Full Professor and Senior Researcher at the Institute of Medical Informatics, Statistics and Documentation at the Medical University of Graz, Austria. He has a long record of research and development in the field of biomedical terminologies, ontologies, and processing of medical language, recently focussing on secondary use scenarios for clinical routine data.

He will present his achievements and his vision for bridging natural and formal languages for representing knowledge and information[7][8][9].

Patrick Ruch is chair of the EFMI NLP working group and a professor in the Information Sciences department of the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO) in Geneva. He is also leader of the Text Mining group of the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, which maintains text analytics services to support the curation of premier molecular biology and translational databases such as Swiss-Prot and neXtprot (~ one million queries a year). Before these appointments, he has been working for more than twelve years in different clinical & research environments, including the University Hospitals of Geneva, the National Library of

Medicine (Bethesda, MD) and IBM Research in Zürich, where he developed text-driven decision support systems for life scientists and healthcare professionals.

He will present his accomplishments and outlooks on clinical encoding and deep question-answering for biomedical decision support [10][11][12].

Jianying Hu is chair of the AMIA Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDDM) working group and a Principal Research Staff Member and Manager of Healthcare Analytics Research at IBM T. J. Watson Research Center. For the past five years her group has been focusing on developing advanced machine learning, data mining and visual analytics methodologies for deriving data-driven insights to facilitate “learning health systems”. The group has conducted widely published research around patient similarity analytics, predictive modeling, temporal event modeling, care pathway analytics, and visual analytics to support patient cohort analysis and disease and treatment progression analysis.

Jianying will discuss examples where features extracted from unstructured clinical notes using NLP can be effectively combined with those from structured data to improve predictive modeling accuracy as well as interpretability in the healthcare domain [13][14][15].

Ronald Cornet is founder and former chair of AMIA KR+S WG and visiting associate professor at Linköping University and assistant professor at the University of Amsterdam. His research focuses on evaluation and use of formal ontologies [16][17][18]. He will moderate the Workshop, facilitate the discussion and instigate the audience to involve.

Workshop Structure and Arguments

The event will provide presentations from 5 speakers as outlined above, followed by a plenary panel-like discussion.

Specific Educational Goals

Attendees will gain an overview of the interactions between (big) data, semantic resources and natural language processing, as shown in Figure 1. All presentations will be made available on the web, together with a wrap-up of the discussions. A position paper, co-ordinated by the LaMB WG, is intended as a spin-off, as well as further collaboration between the participating working groups.

Expected Attendees

Informatics professionals from all areas of practice (leaders in healthcare, healthcare informaticists and IT professionals, vendors, clinicians, researchers, and educators) should find this workshop contemporary and relevant to current issues with knowledge representation and acquisition in the context of Big Data. The topics contained in this tutorial are timely and pertinent to many different professional disciplines.

Figure 1 - The interplay between (big) data, semantic resources and natural language processing

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